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PS2: Reliability of OHL, Advanced Construction and Maintenance (joint PS with C4)

Design & Implementation of “Intelligent Alarm” application for Situational Awareness and Systematic Analysis

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SUMMARY

We have established Control Centres for centralized remote monitoring and control of transmission system comprising overhead transmission lines & substations, introducing a paradigm shift in operation. As of now, more than 270 No. of EHV substations located across length and breadth of country are being remotely operated from control centres.

SCADA System processes more than one lakh (~0.1 million) analog signals and more than five lakh (~0.5 million) status signals and presents at control centres for visibility of substation's asset health to operators for remote operation and monitoring. Each event/alarm in SCADA need to be analysed, prioritised, responded, notified & followed up with remote maintenance personnel as per the case within a particular timeframe to avoid further aggravation of situation, which may sometimes lead to any undesirable incident in grid or equipment failure.

The asset operators at remote control centre have a challenging task of analysing alarms, correlation of events, and evaluation of the situation by applying logical checks manually. The condition extends more stringent during collective receipt of substantial number of alarms from different substations. To optimise & improve operator response in real time and avoiding miss of any alarm, the “Intelligent Alarm” Application has been conceptualised and developed with in-house domain expertise to support remote operation and monitoring with better situational awareness and systematic analysis.

In order to extract actionable information from influx of events, “Intelligent Alarm” Application publishes the processed information on web dashboard as well as inform to concerned engineers through auto-mailers for Operational Awareness and to enhance Data Driven Decision making for transmission asset operators. Following are the noteworthy features of such digitalisation:

1. Alarms categorization with ‘Equipment Type and Signal Criticality’ is being done upon satisfying certain criteria like alarm persisting for defined time interval, correlating the status of related signals, and duly excluding alarms pertaining to equipment under planned outages.

2. Facility to drill down historical details of alarm, in terms of its repetition frequency and action taken earlier.
3. Substation Devices Health monitoring (Gateway & BCU)
4. Auto capture and analysis of SOE related to an outage for auto-segregation like tripping (DT received or other), local operation, Operator action.
5. An auto-email facility to send fault tower details like GPS map link, tower type, conductor position, TLM jurisdiction based on fault distance.
6. Health indexing of CT and CVT assets on real time data to monitor the drift in current and voltage for predictive maintenance to avoid failures coupled with consequential damages.

The following noteworthy challenges have been addressed during digitalisation initiative and transformation through “Intelligent Alarm” Application to achieve the desired performance:

- a) Data validation and quality issues
- b) Cyber security concerns in OT system,
- c) Optimization of data storage for raw and analysed data as per data retention
- d) Linking of unique key across all applications and database

Detailed elaboration on each feature, design and implementation algorithm of Intelligent Alarm application and additional amplification on issues faced and conceivable scope for improvement is illustrated in this paper.

Technological advancement done for digitalisation & data analysis support the operational excellence of transmission system. Further, optimised asset management is primitive as well as crucial step towards environmental measure.

KEYWORDS

Situational awareness- Data Driven Decision making- Predictive maintenance- Drilling down historical detail- Correlating the status of related signal- Utilisation of huge data for systematic analysis- Digitalisation.

DESIGN & FEATURES OF INTELLIGENT ALARM APPLICATION

The intelligent alarm application is designed to cover primarily operational, predictive maintenance and auto-mailer for MIS along with data validation aspects based on data of different subsystem applications. The data is being fetched from application databases of SCADA, RAS (Remote Accessibility System), AFAS (Automated Fault Analysis System), VMS (Visual Monitoring System) using API for data mining and publishing processed data as per flow chart detailed under:

Figure-1 Data Flow Chart of Intelligent Alarm Application

Web dashboard provides specific actionable information through customized webpages for daily-monthly reports, substation summary to operator & Management Information System (MIS). Home page for navigation to unique features is as follows:

Figure-2 Intelligent Alarm Application Dashboard

The flow chart notion of data, visualisation and user interaction for knowledge is elaborated below:

Figure-3 Data Visualization & Exploration

The application has been implemented using web framework (ASP.NET Core, Django) and database (Postgres, MSSQL). The web dashboard is operationalised at all 11 nos. control centres. The detailing of significant features/aspects with usage is elaborated in next paras with three broad categories- Operation, Predictive maintenance, and MIS.

I. For Operation:

1. Critical Alarm dashboard:

Alarms reporting in SCADA are analysed and published upon satisfying certain criteria like persistent for defined time interval, correlating with related signals and duly excluding alarms pertaining to equipment under planned outages. It helps operator to visualise critical alarms immediately and record the corrective action.

Figure-4 Intelligent Alarm Processing

Frequency of alarm received in defined time period is also published to know repetition of particular alarm.

For selected alarms, Email and SMS alerts are being sent to concerned person for immediate information and needful action. Thus, it supports escalation of alarm to expedite rectification based on criticality.

Operator action/response entry option is provided for each alarm received in portal. The historical record along with username, remark's timestamp, console IP etc is being maintained in database for detailed analysis of specific alarm in future and auditing at a later stage.

Persisting alarms are automatically selected for monthly benchmarking of substations/groups on daily basis based on no. of persisting hours and user entered remarks. Customized webpages for daily briefing to management are also available as below:

- a) >24hrs persisting abnormal as well as suspect alarms
- b) Alarms received in last 24 hrs
- c) Remarks entered in last 24 hrs
- d) Monthly summary

		TOTAL ALARMS PERSISTING (Good Quality) AT ALL					
		Alarms persisting 25		No. of substations 17			
CIRCUIT BREAKER		REACTOR		TRANSFORMER		CT TROUBLE	
Emergency 1	Critical 2	Emergency 2	Critical 0	Emergency 0	Critical 0	Alarms persisting 0	No. of substations 0
TRIP Circuit Faulty 0	Low SF6 gas 0	OTI 1	Low oil level 0	OTI 0	Low oil level 0	Gas Alarm at GIS SS	
OPERATION Lockout 1	Spring discharge/Low press/TRBL 2	WTI 0		WTI 0		Alarms persisting 2	No. of substations 1
		Bucholz 1		Bucholz 0		FACTS (STATCOM+SVC)	
		Trouble 0		ICT trouble 0		Alarms persisting 3	No. of substations 2

Figure-5 Critical Persisting Alarms

2. Visual Monitoring System (VMS) Health Monitoring:

Visual Monitoring System is installed at each substation, and it acts as virtual eye of operator at control centre for visibility of remote unmanned substations during operation and routine monitoring e.g. to verify isolator contacts during operation.

This dashboard monitors the health and publishes the count of Online & Offline camera (Site-wise, region-wise, Total), supports auto segregation of Offline camera for various supply packages and create record of action taken based on operator remarks.

The dedicated script reads required data from VMS database at scheduled time interval, transfer data and finally populates the dashboard application database.

The healthiness of network video recorder (NVR) installed at each location for communication of camera with server application at Control Centre is also being monitored and listed on the portal.

The snapshot of VMS portal is shown as follows:

Figure-6 VMS Health Monitoring

3. AFAS fault and ERP tower schedule integration (named as Jatayu# dashboard):

Automated Fault Analysis System (AFAS) is installed at control centre for auto analysis of DR files received from protection IED at substation. The fault details of transmission lines are calculated by AFAS based on DR file having voltage & current waveform data along with digital channels. However, few important parameters like GPS coordinates of towers/ transmission line etc are not available in AFAS reports.

Jatayu dashboard has been developed to supplement the AFAS fault details with tower schedule database in ERP and publishes the other important physical features of fault location viz. exact tower location, GPS coordinates, conductor position for better assessment of fault.

The flow chart elaboration is as follows:

Figure-7 Jatayu# Dashboard

Also, auto-mailer has been configured to share these important details with concerned for further needful.

Jatayu (जटायु) is a demigod in the Hindu epic Ramayana, who has the form of either an eagle or a vulture.

II. For Predictive Maintenance:

1. Voltage Drift Monitoring for CVT Health Assessment:

Secondary voltage drift has been identified as proven health indicator for CVT. Conventional methods of monitoring the healthiness of instrument transformers have a limitation that fast failures within few days (viz after last measurement of secondary volts) may go undetected and in most of the cases lead to violent failures coupled with consequential damages.

On real time SCADA data, voltage drift is calculated with respect to a healthy voltage reference for predictive maintenance and health indexing of CVT assets, as elaborated below:

- a. Healthy reference voltage is calculated with in a substation by average of individual phase-phase voltage, after outlier detection & removal
- b. Faulty phase is identified for elements having voltgae drift above permissible limits using custom logics.
- c. Bus Section at substation are considered as separate group for calculation to eliminate error.

The problem in reference voltage calculation within a substation is managed with outlier detection and removal logic, as given below:

“Lower extreme”: $Q1 - 1.5 \text{ IQR}$

“Upper extreme”: $Q3 + 1.5 \text{ IQR}$

$\text{IQR (Inter Quartile Range)} = Q3 - Q1$

Q1 and Q3 are the 25th and 75th percentile of the dataset respectively.

Figure-8 Outliers

Based on acceptable and permissible limits of drift in voltage, application classify the asset in distinct categories like healthy /to be monitored in a timeframe /to be replaced immediately.

2. Current Monitoring for hotspots prediction

Hotspots are detected in a substation using thermovision scanning during routine periodic maintenance. In order to continuously predict the incipient hotspot using realtime SCADA data, logic is developed to identify the phase in particular bay in which less current is flowing due to high resistance. Also, health indexing of CT’s is being done using current mismatch between phases. Features like analysing drift over a given time interval based on historical data are provided.

The practical example of isolator hotspot which was observed with significant current drift and attended after shutdown as follows:

Figure-9 Hotspot Prediction

3. Substation Devices Health monitoring:

Gateway and BCU are installed at substation for analog as well as status signals reporting at control centres over IEC60870-5-104 protocol. Healthiness of data acquisition devices like sensors, bay level control & protection devices and gateway is very important for remote operation. There are peculiar use cases where conventional method of detecting unhealthy devices at substation does not work.

During routine remote operation of multiple substations from control centre, it is reasonably not viable for the operator to navigate each substation SLD to identify peculiar type of data reporting issues like specific bays partial data is not reporting. Also, identification of multiple BCU not reporting is difficult with conventional BCU unhealthy alarm through watchdog connection.

Similarly, the rare but critical issue of stale check of data for a substation is not readily accessible to the operator.

The intelligent alarm application is configured to address this problem with following logic:

- a. Based on non-reporting of multiple critical signals in SCADA, a particular BCU is predicted as unhealthy and consolidated list is presented to the operator.
- b. The values of Current, Voltage and Frequency of each feeder of particular substation are captured every 15 minutes for identifying the freeze/stale state. If the value does not change by more than 0.1 (one place after decimal) for three consequent samples then that Substation data is declared as hang/freeze/stale.

Figure-10 Data Stale Check

The above features help to ensure reliability of available data and enhance efficiency of remote monitoring of an unmanned substation.

III. Auto-mailers for MIS Reporting:

Auto-mailers plays significant role for managing round the clock remote operation of multiple substations from control centre by delivering right information to right person at right time to ensure timely action. Following Auto mailers has been configured for intelligent alarm application:

Table-1 List of Auto-mailers

S. No.	Description of Auto-mailer	Frequency	Usage
1	Critical alarms summary	Daily @10:30	For escalation and benchmarking
2	Summary of relay block in AFAS to skip DR files processing	Daily @20:00	For review and escalation
3	Listing of bays having Isolator close and CB open for more than defined period	Every 2 hours	For review and escalation
4	Summary of ICT n-1 contingency violation and Transmission line peak loading for 24 hours	Daily @5:00	For review by Asset Management department
5	Real time SOE for any tripping of transmission line, ICT	On exception basis	For tripping analysis along with DR files & AFAS report

Flow chart for real time SOE during tripping is given as following:

Figure-11 Auto-mailer for Fault SOE

CHALLENGES FACED

The Intelligent Alarm application is put in operation, finetuned and enhanced based on feedback and experience of remote operation. The lessons learnt and challenges faced during development and operationalisation of application are as follows:

- a) Training & collaboration with operators for required usage during remote operation & monitoring.
- b) Ensuring point to point data validation and other data quality issues during integration of new element/substation with control centre in coordination with substation team.
- c) Technical difficulties (like compatibility issues, customised API usage, manual mapping of foreign key etc) during data integration with various subsystems i.e., SCADA, Automated Fault Analysis System (AFAS), Remote Accessibility system (RAS) and VMS.
- d) Configuration of redundancy in application and database for remote disaster recovery (DR) site.
- e) Collaboration with OEM/vendors for migration of dashboard during complete system upgradation.
- f) Patch management, routine database maintenance, backup-restoration, and version management of inhouse application.

SCOPE FOR IMPROVEMENT

After usage of intelligent alarm application for more than two years, conceivable scope for improvement includes following:

- a) More inclusion of artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) with proven rule-based approach for data mining i.e., uncovering patterns and other valuable information.
- b) Seamless integration of various application databases through relational database design.
- c) Assimilation of OT domain application with IT domain intranet with latest cyber security guidelines and practices for broader visibility.
- d) Configuration of client application for individual site maintenance engineers.

CONCLUSION

The “Intelligent Alarm” Application has proven effective to drive predictive maintenance and immediate corrective actions at site, ensuring human safety. In short, it may be called as important “line of defence” against major disturbances and safety aspects.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

[1] This paper is based on incessant improvement with experience of centralised remote operation.

Abbreviations

AFAS:	Automated Fault Analysis System
BCU:	Bay Control Unit
CT:	Current Transformer
CVT:	Capacitive Voltage Transformer
DR:	Disturbance Record
ERP:	Enterprise Resource Planning
RAS:	Remote Accessibility System
SCADA:	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SOE:	Sequence of Events
VMS:	Visual Monitoring System